

Nature-based solution as decentralized greywater treatment to minimize the input of personal care products into centralized wastewater treatment plant

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Abstract

In this study, the monitoring of personal care products from influent and effluent in an urban wastewater treatment plant indicated their insufficient elimination with an average efficiency not exceeding 50% removal by conventional treatment technologies in centralized solutions. A possible solution to this is on-site greywater treatment using vertical-flow constructed wetlands filled with biochars produced in a circular economy perspective, such as from plant residues and from sewage-cellulose, which can achieve a removal efficiency of >80% for these micropollutants.

Keywords (maximum 6 in alphabetical order)

Innovative admixtures in constructed wetlands, on-site greywater treatment, personal care products.

INTRODUCTION

Personal care products (PCPs) are represented by shampoos, soaps, toothpastes, perfumes, insect repellents, sunscreen creams, and others, which are routinely used in people's activities and washed in showers and hand sinks, becoming part of the greywater (GW) fraction of domestic wastewater.

Most of these micropollutants are not completely removed from wastewater in centralized wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs), which were not originally conceived for this purpose (European Parliament and the Council of the European Union, 2013; Katsikaros & Chrysikopoulos, 2021). Therefore, they enter the aquatic ecosystem and can represent a potential risk.

Micropollutant emission in surface water is already subject of the revised Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (European Commission, 2023) in which the EC is requiring member states their mandatory monitoring and defining a post-treatment step to upgrade existing WWTPs. The choice of target compounds is based on the so-called watch list (Loos et al., 2024), which in the last version- the fourth already included the UV filter agents oxybenzone (Chemical Abstracts Service-CAS 131-57-7), octocrylene (CAS 6197-30-4) and avobenzone (CAS 70356-09-1). This highlights the importance of PCP monitoring in GW, which is the main source of these pollutants.

Centralized WWTPs could benefit from decentralized GW treatment due to the removal of PCPs at the pollution source, thus reducing the need for an additional polishing step. Moreover, potable water could be saved by reusing the treated water for non-drinking purposes. In Luxembourg, 27% of potable water could be saved by reusing water for flushing toilets (VDL-Luxembourg, n.d.).

A promising GW treatment has been studied at the University of Luxembourg in the 'Removal of personal care products by microbial processes in constructed wetlands for greywater recycling in sustainable building' (ReCare) project, in which vertical-flow constructed wetlands (VFCWs) filled with innovative admixtures produced in the circular economy perspective such as biochar from plant residues and from sewage-cellulose are tested and already presented removal efficiencies of >80% for the majority of target PCP compounds (Muniz Sacco et al., 2024).

In this context, this study aims to assess the effects of decentralised GW-treatment on centralised WWTPs, using VFCWs filled with innovative admixtures as a proposed solution. For this, target PCP compounds in real light GW (RLGW) from a Luxembourgish public school and in the influent and effluent of the urban WWTP which connects the region have been investigated to characterize the seasonality of their concentration over the year, as well as the obtained removal efficiency.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

ReCare is a 4-year PhD project funded by the Luxembourgish National Research Fund (FNR), in which six VFCWs were fed intermittently and simultaneously with synthetic greywater (SGW), in a vertical-flow configuration, three times per day during 30 minutes, with a daily inflow of 7.2 L each and Hydraulic Loading Rate (HLR) of $100 \text{ L d}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$ (Figure 1). The VFCWs were planted with the same mix of plants (*Phragmites australis* and *Iris pseudacorus*) and lighted 8 hours per day (LED lamps). In this study, only results of light SGW (LSGW) are discussed, with the operation period of 108 days, in which 777.6 L of water were treated per VFCW.

Figure 1. Scheme of the laboratory installation of the ReCare project: the influent direction to the lysimeters (L) is indicated by grey dashed lines, and the effluent sampling by grey solid lines. The substrate composition are L1: 85 % sand +15 % zeolite, L2: 95 % sand +5 % zeolite, L3: 85 % sand +15 % activated biochar from plant residues, L4: 95 % sand +5 % activated biochar from plant residues, L5: 85 % sand +15 % activated biochar from sewage-cellulose, and L6: 95 % sand +5 % activated biochar from sewage-cellulose) (Muniz Sacco et al., 2024).

For the monitoring of PCPs in real light GW from showers and hand sinks (RLGW), a Luxembourgish public school located in the North of the country was chosen, which is so far the only example of GW separation in the country, and therefore, it allowed the monthly sampling campaigns. The school was founded in 2018 with around 1,400 students between four- and nineteen-years old, and is connected to the centralized WWTP of Clervaux city serving with a population of c.a. 6,021 Inhabitants, thus monthly sampling campaigns of the wastewater influent and effluent (RWWT) have been carried out there (Figure 2).

The target PCPs (Table 1) were analyzed at the Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST, Luxembourg) by performing the Liquid Chromatography and Tandem Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS/MS), which the methodology is described elsewhere (Muniz Sacco et al., 2024).

Figure 2. Scheme of the PCP monitoring in real light GW (RLGW) at the Luxembourgish public school and wastewater influent and effluent (RWWT) at the urban WWTP in Clervaux.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The monitoring of the PCP concentration listed in **Table 1** has been carried out since March 2024. Out of the listed compounds, only eleven were detected at concentrations higher than LOQ in the wastewater treatment influent. Six of them were present in the RLGW at the case-study school: Diclofenac (DCF), Miconazole (MIZ), N,N-diethyl-meta-toluamide or diethyltoluamide (DEET), Propylparaben (PrP), Nonylphenol (NP) and Oxybenzone (OXY). However, this monitoring must be analyzed the entire year to have conclusive results.

Table 1. PCP and pharmaceutical compounds selected for the micropollutant spike in the LSGW (ReCare project) and monitoring at real condition in RLGW (Luxembourgish public school) and influent of municipal WWTP (Clervaux-LU). Preliminary characterization of these compounds.

Category	Group	Sub-group	Compound	CAS number	Abbreviation	Analytical level of quantification (LOQ) - ng/L	Measured sample - ng/L (n:1) RLGW	Measured sample - ng/L (n:9) WWTP	
Pharmaceuticals	Anti-inflammatories		Diclofenac	15307-86-5	DCF	10	174	585	
			Clotrimazole	23593-75-1	CLOT	25	<LOQ	< LOQ	
	Antimycotics		Fluconazole	86386-73-4	FCZ	10	<LOQ	56	
			Miconazole	22916-47-8	MIZ	25	32	32	
		Antiseptics		Triclosan	3380-34-5	TCS	100	<LOQ	< LOQ
		Insect repellent		N,N-diethyl-meta-toluamide or diethyltoluamide	134-62-3	DEET	10	142	46
PCPs	Preservatives	Parabens	Methylparaben	99-76-3	MeP	100	<LOQ	< LOQ	
			Ethylparaben	120-47-8	EtP	25	<LOQ	< LOQ	
			Propylparaben	94-13-3	PrP	25	155	35	
			Butylparaben	94-26-8	BuP	25	<LOQ	< LOQ	
	Surfactants	Phthalates	Di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (metabolites):	117-81-7	DEHP	-	-	-	
			Mono(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate	4376-20-9	MEHP	25	<LOQ	344	
			Mono(2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl) phthalate	40321-99-1	SOH-MEHP	25	<LOQ	< LOQ	
			Mono(2-ethyl-5-oxohexyl) phthalate	40321-98-0	Soxo-MEHP	25	<LOQ	< LOQ	
		Non-ionic surfactants		Nonylphenol	84852-15-3	NP	100	112	268
				Octylphenol	1806-26-4	OP	100	<LOQ	108
UV-filters			Avobenzone	70356-09-1	AVO	100	<LOQ	213	
			Octocrylene	6197-30-4	OC	100	<LOQ	152	
			Oxybenzone	131-57-7	OXY	10	23	24	

Considering the average concentration of the 11 PCP compounds found in the inlet-WWTP: DCF, FCZ, MIZ, DEET, PrP, MEHP, NP, OP, AVO, OC and OXY (**Table 1**), the overall removal obtained at the case-study WWTP was less than 51% (**Figure 3**), which indicates that conventional processes in centralized mechanical-biological treatments present medium towards poor removal of these micropollutants. Comparing these values to the removal efficiencies of the ReCare project for the same compounds (Muniz Sacco et al., 2024), significant higher values were obtained for all of them (**Figure 3**). Even for the OC, with lower removal efficiency of 84%, was still higher than the removal found in the case-study WWTP (with 32%). Therefore, VFCWs with sustainable soil materials, as a decentralized treatment, is a promising solution for the PCP removal from GW. Besides this, potable water could be saved by reusing the treated water in sustainable buildings.

Figure 3. Removal efficiencies achieved in the ReCare project compared to those of the WWTP case study for the same 11 PCP compounds: Diclofenac (DCF), Fluconazole (FCZ), Miconazole (MIZ), DEET, Propylparaben (PrP), Mono(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (MEHP), Nonylphenol (NP), Octylphenol (OP), Avobenzone (AVO), Octocrylen (OC) and Oxybenzone (OXY).

CONCLUSION AND NEXT STEPS

The PCP monitoring in the influent and effluent of urban WWTPs indicated so far, their insufficient removal by conventional treatment technologies in centralized solutions.

On-site greywater treatment by using vertical-flow constructed wetlands filled with biochars produced in the circular economy perspective, such as from plant residues and from sewage-cellulose, indicated to be a promising solution for the PCP removal with an average of > 84% of removal efficiency. Moreover, potable water could be saved by reusing the treated water for non-drinking purposes.

The PCP monitoring in RLGW and WWTP is being carried out to characterize the seasonality of their presence in the real light greywater and urban wastewater over the year; This may help with the dimensioning and design of the proposed GW treatment upscaling, and to assess the effects of decentralised GW-treatment on centralised WWTPs.

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